

BASIC CONCEPTS AND TERMS IN SOCIAL MEDIA

Otabek RAHIMOV,

**1st year master's student at the International
Innovation University in Karshi**

Some people describe social media as a marketplace, others as a store. Simply put, social media is advertising in everyone's pocket. It's no secret that millions of dollars are being made from social media posts and promotions these days.

All businesses can benefit greatly from social media. Whether you have 500 customers or 1 million, it can help you build your brand on social media.

Social media is an interactive technology that creates and shares information, ideas, interests, and other forms of expression or business information through virtual communities and networks. The main social media channels include Facebook, Instagram, Tiktok, Twitter, Youtube, and Snapchat.

Most businesses choose one or more social media channels to showcase, promote, and promote themselves, thereby signaling their presence in the market.

Social media is a powerful tool for building a successful business. Marketing and advertising are used to build brand awareness and build customer trust. It is also designed to attract new customers and increase market share.

Social media is essentially free marketing and advertising. Although you can also use paid advertising, social media can increase trust and make your brand more relatable.

Compared to traditional advertising methods, social marketing is often cheaper, making it suitable for businesses with limited budgets or those just starting out. Even other experienced and well-known entrepreneurs can use social media to market their products. For example, Nike conquered social media with the slogan

“Just Do It.” With this slogan, the company gained a lot of recognition, fame, and customers. Therefore, loyalty and trust are important for attracting customers and operating successfully.

Regular communication on social media platforms helps to strengthen strong relationships with customers. In short, social media, especially viral posts, is undoubtedly one of the fastest ways for businesses to expand their market. Thanks to social media algorithms, we can show new and potential customers the results of a targeted social plan, which, it is worth noting, automatically expands the market.

Social media acts as a bridge in increasing potential customers for brands. When we say that social media brings brands closer to consumers and strengthens trust between them, we are saying the same thing. To be more precise, social media is radically different from traditional advertising. In traditional advertising, you strive to sell a product or service. On social media, on the contrary, you gain people’s trust by offering valuable information and insights that are necessary for them. This increases consumers’ interest in your brand, service, and product. In other words, social media establishes a strong connection between the company and the customer. You see, your reputation in the market will increase and your product will become popular.

In fact, today, social networks, which are interpreted as “communication power”, are being used as a means of gaining experience, gaining reputation, becoming known, becoming famous, creating your own brand, gaining trust, and developing a business. Close communication on social networks, quick responses, and leaving necessary comments are of great importance in gaining customer trust. Most importantly, firstly, social media provides direct channels for dealing with customers. Through these channels, you can directly learn about customer problems and solve them immediately. Secondly, with the help of social media platforms, you will learn about the interests, needs, and demands of your customers. This will serve to improve the marketing strategy of enterprises.

Your success in social networks is determined by activity, consistency, and speed. It is permissible to post a message or information at the most convenient time.

You should always be in the eyes of customers with your activities. If you slow down, your customers may turn to your competitors. Because competing businesses also try to use social media effectively, “get the ball rolling,” and always be ahead. That’s why it’s important to monitor your competitors. If necessary, competitor analysis can also teach you a lot.

Increasing website traffic is also important. Because the more customers visit your website and spend time using it, the more your income will increase.

Influencers can help you build brand trust and expand your audience. Because now, from entering the market to increasing the number of customers, social networks have become the most powerful marketing of the XXI century.

Customer feedback is especially crucial for brand growth. Customer feedback is very important for improving product quality or service. Social media platforms allow consumers to express their opinions, attitudes, and leave comments. Businesses that listen to their customers who have become their close friends will definitely succeed. An active or loyal customer is one of the most effective advertisements. Because he promotes the brand, posts about the product or service. This customer's post increases trust in the brand. Because he bought the product or used the service, customers trust him. The company will repost this content and increase the number of its customers. It is also important to hire more qualified and talented employees for this.

Social media trends change daily, weekly, and throughout the year. Researchers say capitalizing on these trends can help you grow your customer base: *"Taking advantage of these trends can also increase the potential for viral (advertising) with significant impact in a short period of time."*

Social media analytics show that we can come across many concepts and

terms such as “Likes”, “Shares”, “Engagements” and “Followers”. Most importantly, we need to use the concepts, terms and terminology in social networks purposefully and appropriately.

In short, today social media has become a huge market and an influential tool.

References.

1. Nurmatov Z. Media savodxonlik va axborot madaniyati. -Termiz, Termiz, 2023.-348 .
2. Muratova N., Griel., Mirzaxmedova D. Jurnalistikada media va axborot savodxonligi. -Toshkent, Baktria press, 2019.-112 b.
3. Murotova N., Qosimova N. va boshqalar. Onlayn jurnalistika va mediada yangi trendlar. -Toshkent, O'zbekiston, 2019.-489 b.
4. Media va axboriy savodxonlik.-Bishkek, Modern Journalism development Centre, 2021.-146 c.